

Enantioselectivity of [4+2] cycloaddition between cyclopentadiene and azachalcone with DNA-based hybrid catalyst in aqueous medium: A computational study[†]

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DNA-based asymmetric catalysis is an important subset of hybrid catalysis where the chirality of DNA is utilized to induce the product enantioselectivity of metal-catalyzed reaction. The DNA-based asymmetric catalysis of [4+2] cycloadditions is reported in the literature. However, the origin of the enantioselectivity of such [4+2] cycloadditions is not fully understood. We have examined the origin of enantioselectivity of the Diels-Alder (DA) reaction between cyclopentadiene and 2-azachalcone as a representative reaction in aqueous medium using DFT calculations. To examine the influence of DNA on enantioselectivity, [4+2] cycloaddition has been carried out first in the absence of any catalyst followed by the presence of only copper metal-ligand complex (without DNA) as a catalyst. Finally, the study was performed with DNA-based hybrid catalyst (Cu^{II}-complex) to examine the role of DNA in the formation of enantioselective products. In the absence of any catalyst, there is no enantiomeric preference between two exo- and two endo-products, however, the formation of the endo-products is energetically favorable than the exo-products. The B3LYP and M06-2X DFT functionals predicted one enantiomeric endo-product is favored over the corresponding other enantiomeric endo-product in the presence of the DNA-based hybrid catalyst. The computed results show that the geometries of the endo transition states with DNA hybrid catalyst can induce the enantioselectivity in such DA reactions. The distortion-interaction model reveals that the endo enantioselectivity of cyclopentadiene and 2-azachalcone arises due to the contribution of distortion energy in the transition state.

Keywords: DFT, Diels-Alder reaction, distortion-interaction model, DNA-based hybrid catalyst, enantioselectivity.

Introduction

The design and development of powerful catalysts is one of the ongoing challenges in the modern synthetic chemistry and is very important for the synthesis of natural products, pharmaceuticals, and agrochemicals¹⁻⁶. The hybrid catalysts involving the transition-metal complexes combined with the chiral architecture of biopolymers is of current interest^{2,7-11}. In the area of chemical synthesis, the highly selective and efficient enzymes can be used as a biocatalyst of particular interest^{1,12}. It is seen that a large number of the enzymes require a metal ion cofactor as a prosthetic group to function properly¹³. Such metalloenzymes have shown great prospect in the field of enantioselective catalysis¹³. The highly enantioselective catalytic transformations like hydrogenation, hydrolysis, epoxidation, sulfoxidation, Diels-Alder reactions,

transamination, and allylic alkylation by using proteins as the scaffold have been reported in the literature^{7,12}. Polynucleotides such as DNA and RNA are used as an attractive alternative chiral scaffold for the assembly of enantioselective chiral catalysts^{1,4,12}. In this regard, a hybrid catalyst is made by binding a catalytically active metal complex to a DNA scaffold, which permits the unique chirality of DNA to be transferred into enantioselectivity in the catalyzed reaction. This hybrid catalyst has been implemented successfully in various catalytic enantioselective reactions such as Diels-Alder, Friedel-Crafts, Michael reactions, fluorination and the *syn*-hydration of enones¹⁴. Diels-Alder (DA) reactions are one of the most valuable and important C-C bond forming cycloaddition reactions in preparative organic synthetic chemistry involving a conjugated diene and a dienophile¹⁵. The bond

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breaking and bond formation in the DA reaction are considered to be a concerted process but not essentially synchronous in nature^{16,17}. In some cases, the DA reaction occurs in a two-step process with a biradical or zwitterionic intermediate¹⁸. DA reactions are largely involved in the preparation of different products like pharmaceutical drugs, agrochemical compounds, flavors, and fragrances in the industries^{19,20}. In the DNA-based asymmetric catalysis, the active copper(II) complex (Cu-L) is positioned in close proximity to the DNA helix²¹ through non-covalent interactions in aqueous medium^{11,22}. The enantiomeric excess (*ee*) of the major product is experimentally observed in presence of DNA-based hybrid catalyzed Diels-Alder reactions whereas without DNA hybrid catalyst, the products were obtained as racemates¹. The enantioselectivity of the DA reaction was varied with the substituents of the ligand, and on the spacer length. The observations speculate that the variation in π - π stacking interactions between the ligand and DNA can govern the enantioselectivity. The enantioselectivity induced in DA reactions with DNA hybrid catalyst has been observed, however, the origin of such process is largely unexplored. In this article, we have examined the origin of enantioselectivity of DNA-based asymmetric catalysis for the [4+2] cycloaddition between cyclopentadiene (CP) and 2-azachalcone as a representative case of Diels-Alder reaction computationally with 2,2-bipyridine ligand to explore the enantioselectivity in this [4+2] cycloaddition reaction^{22,23}.

Computational details:

Full geometrical optimizations were carried out in the gas phase employing the Becke three-parameter hybrid density functional combined with the Lee-Yang-Parr correlation functional (B3LYP)^{24,25}. The DFT (B3LYP) calculations were performed with the 6-31G(d) basis set²⁶⁻²⁹ for carbon (C), hydrogen (H), nitrogen (N), oxygen (O) and phosphorus (P) atoms and for the copper (Cu) atom SDD basis set³⁰⁻³² was used. The B3LYP DFT functional is one of the widely employed DFT functionals for DA reaction as well as for larger systems with Cu transition metal³³⁻³⁸. Frequency calculations were performed at the same level of theory to confirm that each stationary point was a local minimum (with zero imaginary frequency) or a transition state (with one imaginary frequency). Furthermore, we have performed the conformational analysis of 2-azachalcone at B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory to examine whether *E* or *Z* conformations is stable. Single-point calculations were executed at the same

level of theory with a universal continuum solvation model (SMD)³⁹⁻⁴³ in water medium ($\epsilon = 78.3553$) employing the B3LYP/6-31G(d)-optimized geometries. The additional single point calculations at M06-2X/6-31G(d) have been performed in water medium on B3LYP/6-31G(d) optimized geometries. We have further calculated percentage of the enantiomeric excess⁴⁴ as

$$ee = \frac{e^{-\Delta E_{endo-I}^\ddagger/RT} - e^{-\Delta E_{endo-II}^\ddagger/RT}}{e^{-\Delta E_{endo-I}^\ddagger/RT} + e^{-\Delta E_{endo-II}^\ddagger/RT}} \quad (1)$$

where ΔE_{endo-I} and $\Delta E_{endo-II}$ is the relative activation energy barrier for *endo-I* and *endo-II*, respectively, *R* is the ideal gas constant, and *T* = 300 K. All DFT calculations were performed with the Gaussian 09 suite of programs⁴⁵.

Results and discussion

The molecular mechanism of the Diels-Alder reaction between cyclopentadiene (CP) and 2-azachalcone (**1a**) in the absence and the presence of a DNA-Cu²⁺-L based hybrid catalyst has been studied using quantum chemical calculations at B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory in aqueous medium. It is noteworthy to examine the stable conformer of the 2-azachalcone moiety. We have carried out the conformational analysis by rotating the C1-C2=C3-C4 bond manually by 10 degrees using B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory (Scheme 1). The conformational analysis reveals that the *trans* orientation is the most stable conformer. We have used

Scheme 1. The conformational analysis has been performed for the C1-C2=C3-C4 bond.

the *trans* conformer of the 2-azachalcone for further computational calculations. We have computed the energetics of the transition state (TS) geometries of the corresponding *exo*- and *endo*-TSs in aqueous phase in the absence of the DNA-Cu²⁺-L based hybrid catalyst (Scheme 2).

We have located two *exo*-TSs (*exo-I* and *exo-II*) and two *endo*-TSs (*endo-I* and *endo-II*) corresponding to the two enantiomeric *exo*- and two enantiomeric *endo*-products (Fig. 1). The transition state geometries are concerted and asynchronous in nature. The (SMD)B3LYP/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d)

Scheme 2. Schematic representation of the asymmetric Diels-Alder reaction between cyclopentadiene (CP) and 2-azachalcone (**1a**) in absence of catalyst.

calculated activation barriers (ΔE^\ddagger) for both the *exo*-I and *exo*-II TSs are same (19.6 kcal/mol) like its corresponding *endo*-I and *endo*-II TSs (19.0 kcal/mol).

The computed results suggest that the *endo*-TSs are energetically favored over the corresponding *exo*-TSs, which corroborates the experimental results^{13,22}. Further, we have also extended our studies with M06-2X/6-31G(d) level

Fig. 1. *exo*- and *endo*-TS geometries with (SMD)B3LYP/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated activation energies (ΔE^\ddagger) in absence of catalyst. (SMD)M06-2X/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated activation energies (ΔE^\ddagger) are given in parentheses. All the energies are in kcal/mol and distances are in Å. (Colour of atoms: grey-C, white-H, blue-N and red-O).

of theory that shows good results for short- and medium-range dispersions. The (SMD)M06-2X/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated results also follow the similar trend as obtained in the B3LYP/6-31G(d) (Fig. 1). The (SMD)M06-2X/6-31G(d) calculated activation energies are comparatively lower in value than the (SMD)B3LYP/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d).

In Scheme 3, we have represented the DNA-based hybrid catalysis of the cycloaddition between cyclopentadiene (CP) and 2-azachalcone (**1a**) as a representative reaction. In the DNA-based hybrid catalyst, the transition metal Cu^{2+} center acts as a Lewis acid to activate the dienophile by coordinating to its ketone oxygen atom and pyridyl nitrogen atom¹. The active Cu^{2+} center is taken into the proximity of the chiral environment of the DNA double helix through a binding spacer ligand (L) *in situ* (Scheme 3)^{1,4,22,46}.

Scheme 3. Schematic representation of the asymmetric Diels-Alder reaction between cyclopentadiene (CP) and 2-azachalcone catalyzed by a DNA-based hybrid catalyst.

Based on the previously reported DFT study¹³, we have considered octahedral copper complex, $[\text{Cu-L}(\mathbf{1a})_2]^{2+}$ which is interacting with the modeled DNA (AT-GC) base pair extracted from the double strand (ds)-DNA structure (Fig. 2).

The reported DFT studies for the similar type of the spacer ligand (L1) and the substrate dienone (**1b**), showed that during the optimization of the octahedral bis-aqua complex, $[\text{Cu-L1-1b}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$, it tends to form the 5-coordinate trigonal bipyramidal mono-aqua complex, $[\text{Cu-L1-1b}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fig. S1)¹³. The outer sphere water molecule of the complex, $[\text{Cu-L1-1b}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ stabilizes it by ~ 9 kcal/mol than the $[\text{Cu-L1-1b}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ (Fig. S1)¹³. The DFT computed results reveal that the formation of the bis-substrate adduct, $[\text{Cu-L}$

Fig. 2. B3LYP/6-31G(d) optimized modeled copper complex $[\text{Cu-L}(\mathbf{1a})_2]^{2+}$ ($\mathbf{1a}$ = 2-azachalcone) with its 2D schematic presentation (Color of atoms: grey-C, white-H, blue-N and red-O).

$(\mathbf{1b})_2]^{2+}$ from this mono-substrate adduct $[\text{Cu-L-1b}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and an additional substrate ($\mathbf{1b}$) molecule is energetically favored (~ 19 kcal/mol) (Fig. S1, see Supporting information)¹³.

To account for the effect of the copper complex $[\text{Cu-L}(\mathbf{1a})_2]^{2+}$ in the absence and presence of the modeled DNA base pair, we have considered only the formation of major *endo*-products^{13,22}. First we have examined the role of the copper complex, $[\text{Cu-L}(\mathbf{1a})_2]^{2+}$ in the absence of the DNA base pair on the catalysis of the cycloaddition between cyclopentadiene (CP) and 2-azachalcone ($\mathbf{1a}$). The B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated activation barriers (ΔE^\ddagger) for the *endo*-I and *endo*-II TSs are 17.2 and 16.9 kcal/mol respectively (Fig. 3) which are lower than the previous computed activation barriers (~ 19.0 kcal/mol for both *endo*-I and *endo*-II TSs) in absence of the copper complex (Fig. 1). The computed activation barrier (ΔE^\ddagger) of the *endo*-II TS is slightly favorable (0.3 kcal/mol) over the corresponding *endo*-I TS. We have calculated the enantiomeric excess using the eq. (1) and 0.3 kcal/mol leads to a 25% ee.

We have modeled DNA with the AT-GC base pair, which is extracted from the available Protein Data Bank's (PDB ID 4E87) ds-DNA structure for computational simplifications (Fig. 4). We have investigated the cycloaddition between CP and 2-azachalcone ($\mathbf{1a}$) with the copper complex $[\text{Cu-L}(\mathbf{1a})_2]^{2+}$ interacting with the modeled DNA base pairs (AT-GC) as a

Fig. 3. *endo*-TS geometries with their (SMD)B3LYP/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated activation energies (ΔE^\ddagger) for cycloaddition reactions between CP and 2-azachalcone ($\mathbf{1a}$) in presence of copper complex $[\text{Cu-L}(\mathbf{1a})_2]^{2+}$. (SMD)M06-2X/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated activation energies (ΔE^\ddagger) are given in parentheses. All the energies are in kcal/mol and distances are in Å. (Color of atoms: grey-C, white-H, blue-N, red-O, and green-Cu).

hybrid catalyst in aqueous medium. Though there are no reports on the intercalation of copper complex $[\text{Cu-L}(\mathbf{1a})_2]^{2+}$ interacting with DNA base pairs, however, recently similar $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{dppz}]^{2+}$ complex; (phen = phenanthroline; dppz

= dipyrrophenazine), intercalated with DNA has been reported⁴⁷. The crystal structure clearly shows that the [Ru(phen)₂dppz]²⁺ complex is nicely intercalated with the DNA. The [Cu-L-(**1a**)₂]²⁺ complex having similar ligand unit can also intercalate within the DNA base-pairs. Therefore, we have also performed the QM calculations considering the interaction of the 2,2'-bipyridine ligand with the DNA G-C base pairs. The B3LYP/6-31G(d) optimized geometry suggests that the copper complex, specifically, the bipyridine moiety intercalates into the DNA base pair, however, two 2-azachalcone units remain outside of the DNA base pair. The bipyridine moiety of the [Cu-L(**1a**)₂]²⁺ stabilizes by π - π interaction with DNA nucleobases. The π - π interaction distances between bipyridine moiety and adenine are 3.37 Å and 3.54 Å with guanine, whereas cytosine nucleobase is present at 3.68 Å. The calculated geometry suggests that there is no π - π interaction between thymine and bipyridine moiety of the [Cu-L(**1a**)₂]²⁺ complex (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. B3LYP/6-31G(d) optimized modeled hybrid catalyst, (AT-GC)-[Cu-L(**1a**)₂]²⁺ (**1a** = 2-azachalcone). AT-GC is represented in ball and bond model while the [Cu-L(**1a**)₂]²⁺ is represented in tube model. All the distances are given in Å (Color of atoms: grey-C, white-H, blue-N, red-O, orange-P and green-Cu).

We have calculated the *endo*-I and *endo*-II TSs in the presence of the modeled hybrid catalyst at the same level of

the theory. The geometrical analyses suggest that the [Cu-L(**1a**)₂]²⁺ is stabilized by π - π noncovalent interaction with the DNA base pair A-T and G-C while intercalating between two base-pairs. The bipyridine stacked with A-T and G-C base pairs allows 2-azachalcone unit flanked outside to undergo DA reaction with the cyclopentadiene moiety (Fig. 5). The computed activation barriers of *endo*-I and *endo*-II TSs are 18.8 and 16.3 kcal/mol, respectively. In this case, the *endo*-II TS is energetically favored (2.5 kcal/mol) over its corresponding *endo*-I TS (Fig. 5). The *ee* selectivity calculated using the difference of activation barriers is 97% using eq. (1)²¹. Roelfes *et al.* have shown that the very high enantioselectivity of DA reaction could be achieved by hybrid DNA catalyst using different bipyridine ligands²². The experimental report revealed that the enantioselectivity obtained with the 2,2'-bipyridine ligand is ~90%. Therefore, our computational calculation corroborates the observed experimental enantioselectivity of DA reaction by the modeled hybrid catalyst.

It was observed that the *exo*- and *endo*-TSs are more asynchronous in nature in presence of the DNA-Cu²⁺-L based hybrid catalyst compared to the absence of any catalyst (Figs. 1 and 5). The B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory optimized geometries reveal that the [Cu-L(**1a**)₂]²⁺ complex is tilted and less intercalated, hence, the bipyridine moiety achieves less π - π interaction in the *endo*-I and *endo*-II TS structures compared to the DNA-[Cu-L(**1a**)₂]²⁺ complex (Fig. S2). The bipyridine moiety in the *endo*-I TS structure stabilizes by the CH- π (2.81 Å) type-interaction with guanine and π - π interaction with adenine (3.84 Å). On the other hand, the bipyridine moiety is stabilized by the CH- π (3.19 Å) interaction with guanine, π - π interaction with adenine (3.85 Å) and thymine (3.61 Å) nucleobase of the DNA in the *endo*-II TS structure (Fig. S3). The additional π - π interaction with thymine nucleobase in the *endo*-II TS structure plays a decisive role in the formation of the enantiomeric excess of *endo*-products. The M06-2X/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) results also corroborate the B3LYP results (Fig. 5).

To investigate such variance in the energetics of the computed activation barriers of *endo*-I and *endo*-II TSs in the presence of the modeled DNA-based hybrid catalyst compared, with copper complex in absence of DNA base pair (AT-GC) and without any catalyst. We have employed the distortion-interaction model for this cycloaddition reaction

Fig. 5. *endo*-TS geometries with their (SMD)B3LYP/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated activation energies (ΔE^\ddagger) for cycloaddition between CP and 2-azachalcone (**1a**) in presence of modeled hybrid catalyst, (AT-GC)-[Cu-L(**1a**)₂]²⁺ (**1a** = 2-azachalcone). (SMD)M06-2X/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated activation energies (ΔE^\ddagger) are given in parentheses. DNA base moiety has been shown in wireframe. All the energies are in kcal/mol and distances are in Å (Color of atoms: grey-C, white-H, blue-N, red-O, orange-P and green-Cu).

(Table 1). According to this model, the activation energy (ΔE^\ddagger) is composed of the summation of the distortion (ΔE_d^\ddagger) and interaction (ΔE_i^\ddagger) energies, i.e. $\Delta E^\ddagger = \Delta E_d^\ddagger + \Delta E_i^\ddagger$ ⁴⁸⁻⁵². There is no preference between the *endo*-I and *endo*-II TS in the absence of any catalyst. The (SMD)B3LYP/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) computed ΔE^\ddagger , ΔE_d^\ddagger , ΔE_i^\ddagger of the *endo*-I and *endo*-II, TSs are same in values in this case. The slightly energetically favorable *endo*-II TS is observed than *endo*-I TS for the cycloaddition of CP with 2-azachalcone (**1a**) with the copper complex [Cu-L-(**1a**)₂]²⁺ which is mainly due to favorable distortion energy of *endo*-II TS (1.7 kcal/mol) over *endo*-I TS. Here, the distortion energy ΔE_d^\ddagger is predominated over the corresponding interaction energy ΔE_i^\ddagger (Table 1). In the presence of the copper complex [Cu-L-(**1a**)₂]²⁺ with AT-GC base pairs, the more favorable *endo*-II TS can be explained with the favorable distortion energy of the *endo*-II TS (4.5 kcal/mol) over its corresponding *endo*-I TS (Table 1). In

this case also, the distortion energy ΔE_d^\ddagger is predominated over the corresponding interaction energy ΔE_i^\ddagger . It can be mentioned here that the total distortion energy of the TS is calculated by adding the distortion of all the reactants (CP and 2-azachalcone) and catalyst (only [Cu-L-(**1a**)₂]²⁺ and [Cu-L-(**1a**)₂]²⁺ with AT-GC base pairs).

Conclusions

In this article, we have examined the effect of chirality of copper complex [Cu-L-(**1a**)₂]²⁺ with DNA base pairs for the formation of enantiomeric excess (*ee*) of the Diels-Alder product. The DFT (B3LYP) studies for the Diels-Alder reaction between cyclopentadiene (CP) and 2-azachalcone (**1a**) in the presence of the copper complex [Cu-L-(**1a**)₂]²⁺ with AT-GC DNA base pair as a modeled catalyst demonstrate the catalytic activity in aqueous solvent medium. The systematic studies indicate that in the absence of the catalyst, there will be no enantiomeric excess (*ee*) for the formation of any major product because of the similar activation barriers for the corresponding *endo*-I and *endo*-II TS (19.0 kcal/mol). The preference of the one enantiomer over the other is observed from the computed activation barriers (ΔE^\ddagger) for the corresponding transition state geometries at aqueous phase in both (SMD)B3LYP/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) and (SMD)M06-2X/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theories. The preferential formation of *endo*-II TS over *endo*-I TS in presence of the copper complex [Cu-L-(**1a**)₂]²⁺ without AT-

Table 1. (SMD)B3LYP/6-31G(d)//B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated activation (ΔE^\ddagger), interaction (ΔE_i^\ddagger) and distortion (ΔE_d^\ddagger) energies for the reactions between CP and 2-azachalcone (**1a**) in aqueous medium. All energies are in kcal/mol

	No catalyst		[Cu-L-(1a) ₂] ²⁺		(AT-GC)[Cu-L-(1a) ₂] ²⁺	
	<i>endo</i> -I	<i>endo</i> -II	<i>endo</i> -I	<i>endo</i> -II	<i>endo</i> -I	<i>endo</i> -II
ΔE^\ddagger	19.0	19.0	17.2	16.9	18.8	16.3
ΔE_i^\ddagger	-13.6	-13.6	-17.7	-16.3	-15.4	-13.4
ΔE_d^\ddagger	32.6	32.6	34.9	33.2	34.2	29.7

GC DNA base pair and copper complex $[\text{Cu-L-(1a)}_2]^{2+}$ with AT-GC DNA base pair shows that the enantioselectivity of major *endo*-product is mainly governed by the favorable distortion energies (ΔE_d^\ddagger) of the reactants. The distortion energy of *endo*-II TS for the copper complex $[\text{Cu-L-(1a)}_2]^{2+}$ with AT-GC DNA base pair is energetically favoured by 4.5 kcal/mol than the corresponding *endo*-I TS. The calculated results demonstrate that the geometry of the *endo* transition states with DNA hybrid catalyst can induce the enantioselectivity in such DA reactions. The geometric perturbations in DNA hybrid catalysts presumably responsible to generate the enantiomeric excess in products. The arrangement of the intercalated $[\text{Cu-L(1a)}_2]^{2+}$ in DNA base-pairs in *endo* transition states create the spatial discrimination of the dienophilic unit for the approach of diene, which results the enantioselectivity in DA reactions. This study would help to understand the role of geometrical features of such hybrid catalysts to achieve chirality in organic reactions.

Supporting information

Cartesian coordinates of all optimized geometries along with energy and frequency of the TS structures have been given in SI. This information is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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